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№4/2025

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogik, psixometodologik va tabiiy fanlarga
ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 712 sahifa,
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Asos: OAK Pedagogik texnologiyalar va psixologik tadqiqotlar bo’yicha ekspert kengashi tavsiyasi (29-10-2024-y.; №10); OAK Tartib-qoida komissiyasi qarori (30-10-2024-y., №10/24); OAK Rayosatining qarori (31-10-2024-y., №363/5).

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.06.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan №C-5669245
reyestr raqami tartibi bo’yicha
ro’yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310

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PSYCHOLOGY OF SPORT IN THE LIFE OF AN ATHLETE

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the examination of the concept of sports psychology as both a science and an academic discipline applied in the practice of working with athletes across various sports. It focuses on fostering and shaping specific qualities and skills in athletes to help them achieve high performance. The article also explores psychological behaviors and patterns observed in individual sports groups, as well as in the athlete as a distinct personality. The author analyzes the negative mental states that may arise in athletes during their professional careers and discusses effective methods for managing these conditions.

Key words: sports psychology, athletes, psychological preparation, mental state, volitional regulation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola sport psixologiyasi tushunchasini ilmiy fan va akademik fan sohasi sifatida ko'rib chiqadi. U sportning turli yo'nalishlarida sportchilar bilan ishlash amaliyotida qo'llaniladi. Maqolada sportchilarda yuqori natijalarga erishish uchun zarur bo'lgan muayyan fazilat va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish masalalari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, sport guruhlaridagi va sportchining o'zi shaxs sifatidagi psixologik xatti-harakatlari va ularning qonuniyatlari tahlil etiladi. Muallif sportchilar faoliyati davomida yuzaga keladigan salbiy ruhiy holatlarni hamda ularni bartaraf etish usullarini ko'rib chiqadi.

Kalit so'zlar: sport psixologiyasi, sportchilar, psixologik tayyorgarlik, ruhiy holat, irodaviy boshqaruv.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается спортивная психология как наука и учебная дисциплина, применяемая на практике при работе с спортсменами в различных видах спорта. Особое внимание уделяется формированию и развитию у спортсменов определённых качеств и навыков, необходимых для достижения высоких результатов. Также анализируются особенности психологического поведения и закономерности в отдельных спортивных группах, а также у самого спортсмена как личности. Автор рассматривает негативные психические состояния, возникающие у спортсменов в процессе их профессиональной деятельности, и предлагает методы их преодоления.

Ключевые слова: спортивная психология, спортсмены, психологическая подготовка, психическое состояние, волевая регуляция.

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that sports psychology is one of the youngest branches of psychological science. The emergence of this field is necessitated by the unique conditions of sports activities, including the pursuit of maximum achievements, competitive drive (the desire to win), and the experience of intense – and sometimes extreme – physical and mental stress.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose of the work is to study the psychology of sports and its impact on athletes. The tasks of our study are as follows: to analyze the impact of negative mental states on the performance of athletes; to assess the relevance of studying sports psychology in modern times; to identify methods of volitional regulation that do not negatively impact the athlete. Sports psychology is a science that studies the psychological states and behavioral patterns of an athlete during professional sports activities and training. It also examines the formation of the athlete's personality, including the development of methods for volitional resistance against negative mental states.

The field of sports psychology also covers relationship systems such as “athlete–athlete” and “coach–athlete”. The object of sports psychology is the athlete – an individual engaged in any form of sport; the subject

is the patterns of the psyche of an individual athlete. The goal of mastering the academic discipline “Sports Psychology” is to develop students’ understanding of the potential for psychological support and assistance in sports activities, and the possibilities for individual counseling for athletes at various levels (initial training groups, educational and training groups, performance enhancement and elite sports mastery). One of the key factors ensuring the effectiveness of the training process is the level of mental stress.

The mechanisms of activation are complex, yet fundamentally based on emotional-volitional regulation. Emotional regulation is triggered by a strong desire to achieve high performance or under intense emotional experiences, such as fear. Emotions often automatically and unconsciously unlock hidden resources for the athlete. In extraordinary emotional states, intense mental stress emerges, overcoming natural limitations. As a result, the reserve capabilities of the body are revealed and utilized in performance. Volitional regulation refers to the conscious effort to mobilize all physical and mental resources aimed at improving performance. It is based not only on desire, but also on a strong sense of duty and the deep understanding of the need to overcome personal limitations to achieve goals. Mental stress, which accompanies all productive activities, arises during both training and competition, though it differs in nature.

Training-related stress is associated primarily with the process itself and the need to manage increasing physical demands. In contrast, competition-induced stress stems from the pressure of achieving a specific result under extreme conditions. Prolonged high-level stress – especially during monotonous training – can negatively affect athletes. Empirical data from the Volitional Self-Control (VSC) test-questionnaire developed by E. V. Eidman revealed that among extreme sports participants: 84% demonstrated a moderate level of volitional self-control (which is considered the norm); 8% exhibited low levels; 8% showed high levels. Based on this, we can conclude that most athletes possess a moderate level of self-control. However, every athlete – especially those involved in extreme sports – should undergo psychological preparation prior to major competitions. This includes addressing the negative effects of stress and anxiety, as well as critically evaluating their own psychological readiness. To achieve high performance and skill enhancement, athletes must systematically develop the necessary psychological and physical fitness through organizational, longitudinal, empirical, and comparative methods.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methods used in sports psychology to study the psychological characteristics of athletes, coaches, and sports teams are largely the same as those applied in general psychology. These methods are typically divided into four categories: organizational, empirical, and quantitative-qualitative analysis.

Organizational methods determine the strategy of the study and include both comparative (including cross-sectional or age-comparative methods) and longitudinal approaches.

The comparative method is used to examine the psychological states and differences among athletes involved in various sports. This includes athletes of different genders, qualifications, and characteristics of the training process, as well as other influencing factors.

The longitudinal method enables the analysis of psychological and psychomotor states of individual athletes or groups over time, particularly during training. It is important to note that such studies are conducted over an extended period.

Empirical methods are diverse and include objective observation, self-observation, experimental methods, and psychodiagnostics.

Training is also considered a method, as it is inherently connected with the education and development of the athlete’s moral and volitional qualities—such as willpower, the desire to win, goal orientation, self-control, persistence, resilience in facing difficulties, determination, courage, self-confidence, and the ability to exert volitional efforts to overcome obstacles and maintain discipline.

These volitional qualities are not developed as abstract traits but emerge from the specific conditions of sports activity.

In the current era—marked by the increasing professionalization of elite sports and the revival of mass and youth sports—the study of the psychological foundations of volitional development, and the psychological preparation of athletes in various disciplines, taking into account their individual characteristics and sports specialization, is an essential area of scientific inquiry.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In order to avoid negative psychological stress, it is advisable for athletes to know the basics of sports training, as well as to study and master the main types of physical activity. An athlete must independently or with the help of a specially trained coach choose the intensity, variety, and volume of physical exercises to be performed. Also, athletes and their coaches must take into account that rest is an integral part of sports training,

since excessively prolonged physical activity inevitably leads to physical fatigue, and what is most dangerous – to psychological fatigue.

In this case, the athlete, in sports terminology, “burns out.” It is the consistent and systematic alternation of all the above characteristics of sports activity that subsequently affects the physical fitness (agility, speed, strength, endurance) of people involved in sports. According to Yu. V. Baykovsky, author of the book “Fundamentals of Sports Training”, there are general and special physical training types for athletes. [General physical training of an athlete is aimed at the comprehensive development of physical qualities. This type of training is especially important in the early stages of athletic development, as it allows for a significant increase in the overall level of the body’s functional capabilities.] It is this type of physical training that physical education teachers in schools and universities typically provide in order to develop all the above qualities in each individual. Therefore, we can say that the goal of competent physical training is to avoid overload, which in turn helps the athlete protect themselves from serious physical injuries – ranging from muscle and ligament strains to disability and other sport-related conditions – which can lead to anxiety, stress, depression, and ultimately, failure in sports. Special physical training of an athlete is aimed at developing physical abilities specific to the chosen sport, focusing on achieving the highest possible level of performance. From this passage, we can conclude that a person who has chosen a certain sport as a profession must thoroughly study the specifics of both physical and emotional training.

Professional athletes are exposed to psychological stress daily, related to competitive pressure, unfair judging, or adverse weather conditions. To help the athlete cope with such factors, the coach must continuously motivate them, emphasize their uniqueness, offer support, and provide emotional comfort in the face of failure – because athletes, like all people in society, are susceptible to emotions. Today, there are various methods to assess an athlete’s emotional state. One of these is the M. Luscher test, which involves a survey using eight colored cards. Based on the results, it is possible to assess whether the athlete struggles with overcoming physical stress and exerting willpower, whether they are in a pathological emotional state, or whether their body requires longer recovery periods after intensive training. The gender of the athlete plays an important role in sports psychology. Many studies have focused on gender differences in sports, but one fact remains consistent across cultures, countries, time periods, and even social status and wealth – from birth, the upbringing of boys and girls differs significantly.

Boys are usually allowed and encouraged to explore the physical world. Their upbringing is linked to messages such as: be stronger, be braver, be more courageous. Girls, in contrast, are raised in a different atmosphere. Physical accomplishments are generally not expected from them. They are viewed as assistants to their mothers or grandmothers, taught skills aligned with that role, and guided with messages like: don’t hurt yourself, don’t get dirty or tear your dress, stay close and don’t wander far. Thus, from childhood, boys tend to receive more physical training opportunities and are psychologically inclined toward more extreme activities.

They are socially more independent in seeking and choosing physical activity, and therefore, often more prepared for sports. The modern world is changing rapidly before our eyes. What seemed unimaginable ten years ago has now become an integral part of our everyday lives. This applies to nearly all aspects of our existence. Sports, physical education, and healthy lifestyles are also evolving significantly. This did not begin yesterday – in 1896, in Athens, Pierre de Coubertin revived the Olympic movement. Fourteen countries and 241 athletes participated. Not a single woman. At the time, sports were likely perceived as a pastime for the wealthy elite. For an average working person, expending energy on seemingly pointless activities like lifting weights or running appeared strange and unnecessary.

In patriarchal societies, the idea of women participating in sports was even more unthinkable. However, sport inherently contains a competitive, even gambling element – one infused with national pride. Against the backdrop of the military conflicts that shook Europe in the first half of the 20th century, sports began to be taken more seriously. Scientists from various countries, supported by their governments, started to provide a scientific basis for achieving better sports performance. Rulers realized that a strong athlete also makes a strong soldier.

CONCLUSION

Is proper physical activity and balanced nutrition enough? No. It has been shown that an athlete’s moral spirit and psychological state are no less important than the number of correctly executed squats or the consumption of precise proportions of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins.

Time and again, physically weaker opponents—bolstered by moral and psychological strength and guided by the right coaching attitude—have managed to outperform more muscular, resilient athletes who lacked motivation and suffered from psychological fatigue.

Moreover, it was clearly a mistake to assume that women were incapable of significant sports achievements. More than a century of sports history has repeatedly disproven this misconception.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2025. №4

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.